

DESIGN FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS IN EUROPEAN AREAS FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

D2.2 Network building report

Grant Agreement number	: 731031
Project acronym	: OPERAS-D
Project title	: Design for Open Access Publications in European areas for Social Sciences and Humanities
Funding Scheme	: INFRASUPP-03-2016
Project's coordinator Organization	: CLEO-CNRS
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WP and tasks contributing	: 2.2
WP leader	: CLEO/CNRS
Due date	: 30/06/2018
Delivery date	: [25/06/2018]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No731031

DRAFT VERSION

Task 2.2. Network development and community building (M6-18) [Task leader: CNRS-CLEO; Participants: all Beneficiaries]

Task Description : After the identification of the key stakeholders involved in e-infrastructures in Europe and beyond through the landscape study, this task will focus on exploring avenues for the development of a long-term e-infrastructure strategy (identification of strategies and objectives) and community building, with OPERAS having a central role in this new context. Interface between Operas-D and the OPERAS network partners and extended stakeholders will be assured by different means such as events, common workshops to validate results (task 1.3) and an online survey. The survey will be based on findings of the landscape study and will contribute towards gaining actual information on practices that will contribute to e-infrastructure integration across Europe. Further, regular email exchanges and reports will be sent to the Operas stakeholders. This task will help strengthen collaborations and address common minimum standards and good practices with relevant initiatives beyond OPERAS and outside of Europe, as well as explore ways to embed OPERAS in the wider European e-infrastructure ecosystem. Results of this work will be D2.3 on the survey, as well as the network community building report D2.2 (M18)

Community Building

The first step of community building is a two-step survey having the objective to gather more detailed information on the usage and needs regarding open scholarly communication, in particular in the Social Sciences and Humanities.

The surveys are addressed at publishers, librarians and funders and collected information and suggestions about practices, standards, enhanced features and new integrated services. The first results of the survey are published [here](#).

There were two sessions of the OPERAS surveys: one during Spring 2017 (May-June), one during Autumn (Nov.-Dec.). The first session collected general information about the practices in open scholarly communication, information then refined through the second session, which was containing more open questions in order to get as detailed information as possible from the interviewees.

As part of the Network building, the survey for the publishers also contained the proposition to join the OPERAS consortium. Eight publishers showed interest for this proposition.

A further mean of the community building is the sharing information about the initiatives of common interest. An example is the [open air call for proposal about alternative funding mechanism](#) which was disseminated through operas network.

Another ways of community building is the participation to OPERAS Working Group. Each new OPERAS member sends to the operas network a short description of its activities and has a short interview with the coordinator about it's ongoing activities and can choose the participation to an Working group following its specificity. The aim of the working groups

is to address all future activities and more in particular to do research on the their topic, build expertise, and help prepare for future projects. The WG are organized around the following topics: Advocacy for Open access, Tools (R&D), Standards, Business models, Best practises, Multilingualism, Platforms/services.

Working Groups are required to produce a white paper on their topic. Each group, coordinated by an OPERAS core member, has presented their work and a poster at the OPERAS-D final conference which took place from 31 May – 1 June 2018 in Athens, Greece. The white paper are under preparation and will be finalized for 20 July. The executive summaries of each working paper are available on the [Operas website](#).

Network development

In January 2017, at the beginning of the Operas-d b project, the Operas network was composed of 17 partners and the Operas-core group of 5 members.

At the end of the year 2017, the Operas network is composed of 34 partners and the Operas-core group has been enlarged to 9 members.

A [Memorandum of Understanding](#) has been signed within the members of the core group in July for the ESFRI Submission.

At the same opportunity the members have sent letters of support. 17 letters of support have been gathered.

OPERAS Partners

OPERAS gathers 36 organizations from 13 European countries and is coordinated by a 9 members core group. OPERAS is led from France by OpenEdition.

The complete and updated list is available on the [Operas website](#).

New partners have joined Operas in different circumstances, at the preparation phase for the ESFRI submission or after a presentation in a workshop or for an international event. New membership is often linked to a communication activity.

In order to better introduce the development of the Operas network the subscriptions are detailed by months timeline.

January : Ubiquity Press <http://www.ubiquitypress.com/>

February : University of Zadar <http://iz.unizd.hr/>

May : IBL PAN <http://ibl.waw.pl/>

July: The Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences of Nova University in Lisbon : <http://fcsn.unl.pt/>

August :

- Lingoa : <http://www.lingoa.eu/about/mission/>
- Roma Tre : <http://romatrepress.uniroma3.it/ita/>
- Université de Liège : https://www.ulg.ac.be/cms/c_17700/fr/open-access
- AISA : <http://aisa.sp.unipi.it/about-aisa/>

September and October

- SRCE of Zagreb University (HR) : <http://www.srce.unizg.hr/en/>
- Hypothes.is Stichting (NL) : <https://web.hypothes.is/about/>
- Lexis srl (IT) : <http://www.lexis.srl/>

At the beginning of 2018, 2 new members joined OPERAS: UIT, the Arctic University of Norway <https://en.uit.no/om> and the Stockholm University <https://www.su.se/>
Operas network is enlarged to 36 organisations from 13 countries.

International partners : SCIELO <http://www.scielo.org/php/index.php?lang=en>

With some partners the collaboration is reinforced because of ongoing bilateral cooperations with OpenEdition.

With [Lexis](#) for ex. in Italy, there is an ongoing partnership about the project [OpenEdition Italia](#) which promotes the use of the OpenEdition platforms.

In Poland, the project with [IBL- PAN](#) has the objective to promote the Openedition platform and add new contents in Polish and other languages. A pilot has been funded by OpenAIRE through their "[2nd call for funding for non-author fee based publishing initiatives](#)".

In Portugal, as a result of the partnership with [Centro em Rede de Investigação em Antropologia](#) and the [LusOpenEdition](#) project, new members have been added in the country and in Bresil.

In Spring 2018 new collaborations have been sought in Northern Europe, in Spain, Slovenia and Central Europe. New contacts in Nordic country have been prospected also thank to communication action of the [HIRMEOS Project](#).

New partners that are being contacted are :

- Spain : CSIC (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas), UNED (Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia)
- Sweden : Stockholm UP, Goteborg University
- Slovenia : University Ljubljana
- Norway : Tromsø University
- CEEOL : Central and Eastern European Online Library

As stated above Stockholm University and Arctic University of Norway have joined OPERAS in February and March.

The University of Ljubljana has manifested the interest to join Operas, therefore a meeting has been organized in Ljubljana with the University for May 22, where Pierre Mounier, the Operas coordinator has participated to the meeting "Open access in Humanities". At the

beginning of June the Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana sent the support letter and join Operas.

CEEOL (Central and Eastern European Online Library) has been contacted by mail and exchanges have started. Wolfgang Klotz, one of the CEEOL founders participated to the Operas-d final conference. The CEEOL submission is pending at the time of the writing of this report.

After the Operas-d final conference new requests to join has been received.

The Centre for Evaluation in Education and Science (CEON/CEES) from Belgrade, Serbia has shown its interest and is willing to explore avenues for a collaboration. The SME NET7, the University of Hertfordshire Press and the ZRC publishing from Slovenia requested also to join.

The PKP (Public Knowledge project), a multi-university initiative developing (free) open source software and conducting research to improve the quality and reach of scholarly publishing from Canada also initiated discussions to join OPERAS.

At the end of June Operas gathers 37 members from 14 countries.

The last requests are at the moment pending since the submission procedures has to be updated and finalized. Cf. the following paragraph.

How to join Operas

During the Operas-core meeting in Amsterdam on January 2018 the submission procedures have been discussed and a methodology has been setup to establish the procedures for the assumption of new members. The necessity for a new status such as “associate member/observers” seems to be necessary.

The criteria and procedures for admitting new members has been built during two meetings: during the Operas - core meeting in Bonn (23 April) and after the final conference in Athens on 1st of June. During this Operas-core meeting the rules of engagements, requirements for commitment, the types of membership and the application review has been settled and validated.